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Advanced hybrid thermal management system for LTO battery module under fast charging

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, the use of electric vehicles (EVs) equipped with lithium-ion (Li-ion) batteries, has been growing every day. Li-ion batteries' performance, effectiveness, and safety importantly depend on thermal management systems (TMSs). In this paper, a novel and advanced hybrid TMS for cooling the battery module, using phase change material (PCM) and liquid cooling, has been experimentally studied. Passive PCM heat buffer plate and liquid cooling plates are connected from down and lateral sides, respectively. Cooling with natural convection could not preserve the module temperature in the desired operational temperature at fast charging. The average module temperature for the charging and discharging process reaches 41.4 °C and 43 °C respectively. The results display the module temperature equipped with a PCM heat buffer plate at the end of the charging and discharging process reaches 35.8 °C and 36.2 °C which experience a 13.3% and 15.8% temperature reduction, respectively. Using the hybrid cooling system, the module temperature at the end of the charging and discharging process reaches 31.2 °C and 31.8 °C which experience a 24.6% and 26% temperature reduction compared with natural convection. Moreover, using the hybrid cooling system the temperature uniformity has been improved by 56% and 34.8% for the charging and discharging process, respectively.

Nomenclature

Acronyms

EV	Electric vehicle
HEV	Hybrid electric vehicles
Li-ion	Lithium-ion
SOC	State of charge
TMS	Thermal management system

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PCM	Phase change material
CC	Constant current
CCCV	Constant current followed by constant voltage
BMS	Battery management system
OCV	Open-circuit voltage
HPPC	Hybrid pulse power test
NC	Natural convection
LTO	Lithium-titanate-oxide

1. Introduction

Nowadays the global warming and air pollution are among the most world vital challenges [1,2]. Therefore, clean transportation systems like electric vehicles (EVs) and hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs) are being settled to control CO₂ emission, fossil fuel usage, and environmental issues [3]. The demand for high-power EVs has been increased by the continuous developments of electrical devices. Among many sorts of batteries, lithium-ion (Li-ion) batteries have received special attention in recent years [4,5]. Li-ion batteries benefit high-power, high-energy-density, low self-discharge, long-life period, and no memory effect [6–9]. In the meantime, the temperature of Li-ion batteries must be cautiously controlled and preserved to a precise limit specially in high C-rates [10,11]. Normally, C-rate is defining as a rate of charging/discharging of the cell concerning its maximum capacity. The cell temperature has a direct effect on the performance, capacity, and effectiveness of the battery [12,13]. Consequently, it is critical to saving the Li-ion cells in operating temperature of 25 °C–40 °C and the temperature uniformity of less than 5 °C [14,15]. High temperatures probably lead to thermal runaways or serious safety issues like fire and explosion. In addition, temperature non-uniformity in the battery module/pack causes a localized deterioration and state of charge (SOC) mismatches. Therefore, the design of a battery thermal management system (TMS) is required to control and maintain the temperature of the battery in a proper range especially in the fast charge and discharge process [16,17]. Many TMSs have been recently presented for battery cooling which comprises of two main categories of passive and active cooling systems [18]. Liquid cooling, air cooling, refrigerant, and mist cooling are some examples of active cooling systems which need an external source of energy [19–22].

Air cooling is the most common cooling system, which is used in Toyota Prius, Honda Insight, and Nissan Leaf owing to its simple design, low cost, and easy maintenance [23,24]. Behi et al. [25] experimentally and numerically considered the cooling effect of air cooling technology for EVs in four cooling strategies. They designed an air cooling using sandwiched heat pipe system that could decrease the maximum cell temperature by 33.4%. Zhang et al. [26] numerically designed a battery TMS with symmetrical airflow for a battery pack. They considered the effect of inclination angles, battery layout, inlet, and outlet position. Behi et al. [27] investigated a new concept of air cooling for a cylindrical battery module. They not only decreased the maximum module temperature by 34.5% but also increased the temperature uniformity by 39.2%. Wang et al. [28] numerically optimized a Z-type battery air cooling for a prismatic module. They could improve the battery cooling and temperature uniformity by 6.26% and 90.78% respectively. Nevertheless, the air cooling system is not a successful method to achieve the heat dissipation demand under the high current profile and emergency conditions, because of low air heat transfer coefficient and non-uniform temperature distribution [29].

The liquid cooling system provides a higher heat transfer coefficient compared with air cooling [30–32]. The cooling medium comprises water, nanofluids, and ethylene glycol mixture benefit high cooling capacity. Consequently, the liquid cooling system is widely used in several commercial EVs, for instance, Tesla, BYD, and BMW i8. Behi et al. [33] numerically considered the effectiveness of a sandwich side liquid cooling system on a Lithium-titanate (LTO) battery module. They studied the effect of different coolant velocities on maximum module temperature and temperature uniformity. Tan et al. [34] investigated the novel direct liquid cooling system for thermal management of EVs under fast charging. They provided a novel multilayer structure to progress the battery temperature uniformity. Tang et al. [34] designed a lightweight and novel liquid cooling plate for thermal management of prismatic battery module. They numerically investigated the effect of discharging rate, inlet velocity, and cooling structure for the module. Karimi et al. [35] studied the compact liquid-based cooling system for a high-power capacitor. They experimentally recorded the temperatures of 55.7 °C, 44.8 °C, and 32.6 °C for free cooling, forced convection, and liquid cooling thermal management, respectively.

In contrast with active cooling systems, natural convection, phase change material (PCM), heat sink, and heat pipe are classified as passive cooling systems with no external energy [36]. PCM cooling method benefits advantages of no power consumption, high-temperature uniformity, and flexible geometry [37]. The paraffin-based PCM is known as organic energy storage owing to its nontoxic, high latent heat, and low cost. PCMs suffer from low thermal conductivity however, nanomaterial [38], heat pipe [39], heat sink [40], mesh, nanocarbon tube, and other additive materials can compensate for this drawback. Behi et al. [41] experimentally and numerically investigated the cooling effect of PCM with phase change temperature of 30 °C on LTO cell under the high discharging profile. Zhou et al. [42] studied the cooling effect of PCM for the prismatic battery module at different C-rates. They investigated the phase change temperature and mass of PCM for the thermal management of cell. Karimi et al. [43] considered the effectiveness of PCM and PCM aluminum mesh for lithium capacitor module. They numerically studied the effect of PCM thickness and double PCM for thermal management of module.

Heat pipe cooling is another method, which has been widely used in many research and industry applications [44]. It consists of an evaporator, condenser, and adiabatic sections which can transfer the heat very efficiently [45]. Behi et al. [46] designed a novel heat

pipe-based cooling system for the battery module at high discharging profiles. They considered the effectiveness of different cooling scenarios including free cooling, forced air cooling, and evaporative cooling. Alihosseini and Shafae [47] experimentally and numerically studied the battery cooling through the flat heat pipe. They found using the heat pipe raised the setup weight by approximately 10%. Nevertheless, it meaningfully progressed the productivity and aging of the battery.

Hybrid cooling methods have been introduced in order to take the most advantageous benefits of active and passive cooling systems. The special applications comprising high charging/discharging profiles, high-speed traveling, high-power driving mode need the combination of the active and passive cooling systems to control the thermal challenges for battery module/pack. Liu et al. [48] considered the cooling effect of hybrid battery TMS for prismatic cells that couples PCM/copper foam with helical liquid cooling system. They found due to the liquid cooling effect to absorb the excess heat of the cells, the latent heat for PCM with a lower melting point can be more effective. Wu et al. [49] used a structural hybrid liquid cooling with high latent heat PCM for cylindrical battery module. They found compared with liquid cooling system the maximum module temperature and temperature difference are decreased by 42.67% and 38.27%, respectively. Kong et al. [50] experimentally and numerically investigated a new hybrid cooling system using PCM and liquid cooling for cylindrical battery module. They considered the effect of hybrid cooling system in different ambient temperatures, inlet coolant velocity and inlet coolant temperature. To the authors knowledge all the mentioned cases are using the submerged PCM as a passive cooling system. In this method, a specific space should be considered among the cells for an effective cooling system that leads to a volume increase. In our case, a novel PCM heat buffer plate is used as a holder which not only cools down the module but also decreases the volume of the cooling system. In this study, the combination of PCM heat buffer plate and liquid cooling has been used as a thermal management system. The module has been charged and discharged under the 4C discharging rate (92 A) between 10% and 90% of SOC. The combination of the PCM heat buffer plate with the liquid cooling system shows possible commercial value, which can overcome the drawbacks associated with existing thermal management systems. The integration not only decreased the maximum temperature of the module but also increase the temperature uniformity of the module. The presented paper is prepared as follows. Section 2 represents the module development, cell, PCM, and cooling plate properties. Test setup description and methodology are also presented in Section 2. In Section 3, the experimental results and their comparison are illustrated. Finally, a relevant conclusion is drawn in Section 4.

2. Module development

2.1. LTO cell properties

The LTO cell is a kind of rechargeable battery that benefits a long-life cycle, fast charging, and high discharge current. The battery cell consists of NMC in the cathode and LTO in the anode. The anode material is a promising substance with a spinal structure that provides a surface area that is considerably larger than other kinds of lithium-based batteries [51]. Moreover, LTO chemistry has a low risk of thermal runaway and has the ability for a recharge efficiency of up to 98%, which is considerably more than conventional energy storage mechanisms [52]. It can be extensively used in EV charging stations, renewable energy storage power, traffic signals, UPS power supply, and etc. owing to the outstanding features. As the tests are done under fast charging/discharging the 23 Ah battery cell has been carefully chosen for experimental tests. Table 1 presents the main parameters of the cell [53].

For module level, 30 cells are connected in series with no space between the cells. Aluminum pins with a radius of 3 mm and a height of 15 mm are welded on the tabs of the cells. The cells are connected by a copper busbar with the dimension of $30 \times 20 \times 3$ mm in length, width, and thickness respectively. The main features and picture of the module are displayed in Table 2 and Fig. 1 respectively.

2.2. PCM heat buffer plate and liquid cooling

The PCM is integrated into an aluminum plate with the dimension of $860 \times 142 \times 18$ mm in length, width, and thickness respectively. The total weight of the plate is 3438.5 g of which 540.5 g belongs to the PCM. RT35HC from the Rubitherm company has been selected as a PCM for passive cooling [54]. The main features of the PCM are presented in Table 3.

The PCM heat buffer plate connects the module from the downside to act as a passive cooling system and holder of the module. The

Table 1
The main properties of the cell.

Parameter	Value
Chemistry	LTO
Shape	Prismatic
Nominal Voltage (V)	2.3
Maximum voltage (V)	2.7
Minimum voltage (V)	1.5
Capacity (Ah)	23
Specific Energy (Wh/kg)	96
Energy Density (Wh/L)	203
Weight (kg)	0.550
Volume (L)	0.260
Dimensions L × W × H (mm)	115 × 22 × 103
Heat specific capacity (J/kg.K)	1150
Thermal conductivity x,y,z (W/m.K)	31, 0.8, 31

Table 2
The main properties of the module.

Parameter	Value
Number of cells in series	30
Nominal voltage of the module (V)	69
Weight (kg)	16.5
Volume (L)	7.8
Stored energy in the module (KWh)	1.6

Fig. 1. The picture of the module consisting of 30 cells in series.

active cooling section belongs to liquid cooling plates which sandwich the cells from the lateral sides. The cooling plates consist of aluminum plates with one inlet and one outlet. The dimensions of the plates are $694.7 \times 100 \times 4$ mm in length, width, and thickness respectively. It is worthy to mention that the thermal interface material with thermal conductivity of 8 W/m.k is used between the cooling plates and cells to decrease the thermal contact resistance. Fig. 2 shows the PCM heat buffer plate, liquid cooling plate, and battery module equipped with cooling plates.

2.3. Test setup description and methodology

The experimental test setup consists of a module, battery management system (BMS), Accel chiller, PEC battery tester, PICO acquisition system, K-type thermocouples, and a personal computer to control and collect final output data. For cycling the module, the SBT 8050 battery tester (PEC) is used. The voltage and current of the module are controlled by the PEC software interface. The external thermocouples are used to measure the cell temperatures. Different test regimes have been defined to consider the heat generation effect of the module under the different cooling systems. In the current study, the effect of natural convection, PCM heat buffer plate, and liquid cooling has been considered for the module level under the 4C charging/discharging rate. Seven thermocouples with the accuracy of $\pm 0.2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ have been connected to the cell top surface to measure the cell temperatures. It is necessary to mention the whole test setup is located in a room with a constant temperature of $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Fig. 3 shows the schematic of the test setup.

The experimental tests have been done at the module level under the 4C (92 A) charging/discharging process in the Battery Innovation Center (MOBI) laboratory located in the ETEC department of the Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB). The module is charged by constant current followed by constant voltage (CCCV) from 10% to 90% of the state of charge (SOC). Moreover, they discharged by constant current (CC) from 90% to 10% of SOC. To develop the module the characterization of the cells are necessary. Therefore, a number of tests comprising the preconditioning test, capacity test, open-circuit voltage (OCV) test, hybrid pulse power test (HPPC), and validation test are done to check the cell characteristics in a different range of conditions. In order to consider the effect of different cooling methods on the module level three scenarios have been investigated experimentally as follows:

- Considering the natural convection cooling effect on the module under the 4C charging/discharging rate
- Examination of PCM heat buffer plate on the module under the 4C charging/discharging rate

Table 3
The main features of the PCM.

Parameter	Value
Melting domain, ($^\circ\text{C}$)	34–36
Max operation temperature, ($^\circ\text{C}$)	70
Thermal conductivity (Solid-Liquid), (W/m.K)	0.2
Heat storage capacity $\pm 7.5\%$, (kJ/kg)	240
Density (Solid-Liquid), (kg/lit)	0.88–0.77
Specific heat capacity, (kJ/kg.K)	2

Fig. 2. The (a) picture of PCM heat buffer plate, (b) schematic of the liquid cooling plate and dimensions, and (c) picture of module equipped with cooling plates.

Fig. 3. The picture of the test setup consists of (1) module, (2) battery tester, (3) chiller, (4) datalogger, (5) personal computer, and (6) BMS.

- Investigation of the effect of hybrid PCM heat buffer plate and liquid cooling in module level under the 4C charging/discharging rate

3. Experimental results

3.1. Effect of natural convection cooling system

According to the literature review, the temperature of the Li-ion battery module should be controlled in a safe temperature zone of 25 °C – 40 °C, and the temperature difference should be preserved less than 5 °C through the cooling effect of PCM heat buffer plate and water cooling. The first scenario is considering the cooling effect of natural convection on the battery module. A total of seven thermocouples are used to measure the temperature of the module which can be seen in Fig. 4a. The T₁ shows the temperature of cell number 1, T₂ the temperature of cell number 5 and finally, T₇ shows the temperature of cell number 30. Fig. 4b shows the temperature distribution of the module during the charging process from 10% to 90% of SOC. The cell temperatures are increased almost linearly with time. It can be seen the T₁ and T₇ show lower temperatures compared with the other thermocouples due to the free lateral surface which can have more efficient heat transfer to the ambient. The temperature of T₂ - T₆ thermocouples increase linearly from 25 °C to 42 °C. For discharge rate, the condition is almost the same with temperature changes from 25 °C to 44 °C. Generally, the average temperature of the module at the end of the charging and discharging process reaches 41.4 °C and 43 °C respectively. It is obvious the natural convection is seemingly unsuccessful to control the temperature of the module under the 4C charging/discharging rate.

3.2. Effect of PCM heat buffer plate

PCM is considered a passive cooling system that benefits zero power consumption, uniform thermal management, and flexible geometry. In the meantime, paraffin-based PCMs are classified as the most promising energy storage because of the low cost, high latent heat, environmentally friendly, and non-toxic materials. The thermal performance of the PCM heat buffer plate has been considered on the battery module in the following section. The cooling plate is made of aluminum and PCM with a total weight of 3438.5 g of which 540.5 g belongs to PCM. The phase change temperature of PCM is carefully chosen depending on the range of safe battery temperature limit. The PCM heat buffer plate not only plays the role of the holder but also cools down the module from the downside. The thermal energy storage and cooling capacity of the plate have been increased using the PCM. Fig. 5 shows the temperature distribution of the module using the PCM heat buffer plate. The average temperature of the module at the end of the charging and discharging process reaches 35.8 °C and 36.2 °C which experience a 13.3% and 15.8% temperature reduction, respectively, as compared to natural convection.

3.3. Effect of hybrid PCM heat buffer plate and liquid cooling system

Hybrid cooling systems are a new phenomenon to bring the advantages of every cooling system into full play and compensate for their drawbacks simultaneously. The combination of liquid cooling and PCM is an efficient hybrid cooling system due to the advantages of both systems comprising the no power consumption for PCM and high heat transfer coefficient for the liquid cooling system. The heat generation of the module is cooled by the water inside the cooling plates from the sides and by the PCM heat buffer plate from the downside simultaneously. The flow rate and temperature of the inlet water are set at 0.25 lit/s and 25 °C respectively. It

Fig. 4. (a) The schematic location of the thermocouples, (b) temperature variation of the module in charging process, and (c) temperature variation of the module in discharging process at the 4C rate under the natural convection in 700 s.

Fig. 5. (a) The schematic location of the thermocouples, (b) Temperature variation of the module in charging process at 4C rate under the PCM cooling method in 700 s, and (c) Temperature variation of the module in discharging process at the 4C rate under the PCM cooling method in 700 s.

Fig. 6. (a) The schematic location of the thermocouples, (b) Temperature variation of the module in charging process at 4C under the hybrid cooling method in 700 s, and (c) Temperature variation of the module in discharging process at the 4C rate under the hybrid cooling method in 700 s.

can be seen in Fig. 6 the cooling efficiency has been increased by the hybrid cooling method. The average temperature of the module due to the cooling efficiency of the hybrid cooling system at the end of the charging and discharging process at 4C reaches 31.2 °C and 31.8 °C respectively. It is found that the module experiences a 12.8% and 12.1% temperature reduction under hybrid cooling for charging and discharging, respectively, as compared with the PCM cooling method. Moreover, it experiences 24.6% and 26% temperature reduction compared with natural convection for the charging and discharging process, respectively.

3.4. Comparison of module temperature by different cooling methods

The final temperature of the cells within the different cooling strategies in the charging and discharging process are shown in Fig. 7a and b respectively. All the tests are done in constant initial temperature of 25 °C and 4C charging/discharging rate between 10% and 90% of SOC. There is a meaningful temperature variation between the cells and in different cooling methods. In all cases, the temperature of cell number 1 and 30 are lower compared with other cells due to the effect of natural convection on the lateral side of the cells. The temperature of the cells in discharging process is slightly higher than the charging process which is probably related to

Fig. 7. Temperature distribution of the cells (a) in the charging process, and (b) discharging process at the 4C rate under the natural convection (NC), PCM, and PCM-liquid cooling methods in 700 s.

the internal resistance of the cells. It is obvious the hybrid cooling method is a successful and efficient cooling system for thermal management of module in fast charging/discharging. The hybrid cooling system not only controlled the maximum temperature of the cell but also arranged an acceptable temperature uniformity.

3.5. Investigation of module temperature uniformity

Temperature uniformity is classified as a significant index to estimate the effectiveness of a cooling system in battery TMSs. It is frequently used to investigate the maximum temperature difference on the battery cell/module. Generally, lack of adequate temperature uniformity within the battery module leads to different charging/discharging of the individual cells which are consequent in the electrical imbalance of the cells, thus decrease of the module performance. In this study, the maximum temperature difference between the cells has been considered for natural convection, PCM heat buffer plate and, hybrid cooling. Fig. 8 shows the radar chart of maximum module temperature difference for three cooling scenarios at the charging and discharging process. The temperature difference is defined by several triangular from 0 °C to 3 °C. It is clear that the hybrid cooling system has an incredible effect on temperature uniformity. Using the hybrid cooling system the temperature uniformity has been improved by 56% and 34.8% for the charging and discharging process respectively.

4. Conclusion

In this paper, the thermal behavior of the LTO battery module consisting of 30 cells has been considered by different cooling scenarios. The module is charged and discharged under the 4C rate (92A) from 10% to 90% of SOC. Three scenarios comprising natural convection, PCM heat buffer plate, and hybrid cooling have been investigated experimentally. The module temperature exceeds the safe temperature range using natural convection. The average module temperature for the charging and discharging process reaches

Fig. 8. Radar chart of maximum module temperature difference under the natural convection (NC), PCM, and PCM-liquid cooling methods at 700 s.

41.4 °C and 43 °C respectively. The PCM heat buffer plate performs an acceptable cooling efficiency as a passive cooling system. It provides 13.3% and 15.8% temperature reduction for the charging and discharging process respectively. The hybrid cooling system demonstrates a well-balanced design with active and passive cooling systems which is provided a 24.6% and 26% temperature reduction for the charging and discharging process respectively. In addition, it can be an effective TMS to provide temperature uniformity inside the module.

Credit authorship contribution statement

Hamidreza Behi: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Experiment, Investigation, Data curation, Writing - original draft. **Danial Karimi:** Software, Investigation, Validation. **Theodoros Kalogiannis:** Writing - review & editing. **Jiacheng He:** Experiment. **Mahesh Suresh Patil:** Writing - review & editing. **Jean-Damien Muller:** Experiment. **Anita Haider:** Experiment. **Joeri Van Mierlo:** Review & editing. **Maitane Berecibar:** Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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